

An ARZ-Binary Block Code Based on ARZ-algebra

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Abstract

In this work, an ARZ-binary block code is created based on ARZ-algebra which is a generalization of BCC-algebra. An ARZ-valued function is defined to form this code. On various cases of ARZ-algebra, namely commutative and implicative, not commutative and implicative, not commutative and not implicative and commutative and not implicative, the ARZ-codes are existed. Also, the ARZ-code V is a subset of the universal binary block code. Conversely, the ARZ-code can be used to recover the ARZ-algebra. These results are proved mathematically. Some examples are presented to explain these results. The creation of ARZ-code considers as a new insight for communications.

Keywords: BCC-algebra, ARZ-algebra, ARZ-valued function, ARZ-Code.

1. Introduction

A block code is a type of error correcting code. It adds redundancy to a plaintext, so that the receiver can decode a plaintext with minimal errors, provided that the information rate would not exceed the channel capacity. The main characterization of a block code is by a fixed length channel code (unlike source coding schemes such as Huffman coding, and unlike channel coding methods like convolutional encoding) [1]. On the other hand, BCK-algebras were first introduced in 1966 by Y. Imai and K. Iseki, [2] as a generalization of the concept of set-theoretic difference and propositional calculi. The class of BCK-algebras is

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a proper subclass of the class of BCI-algebras and there exist several generalizations of BCK-algebras, as a generalized BCK-algebras [3], dual BCK-algebras [4] and BE-algebras [5, 6]. These algebras form an important class of logical algebras and have many applications in the various domains of mathematics such as: group theory, functional analysis, fuzzy sets theory, probability theory, topology and others. Also, BCK-algebras and their applications, one can be seen [7-13]. One of the recent applications of BCK-algebras was given in the coding theory. In coding theory, a block code is an error-correcting code which encode data in blocks. In 2012, W.A. Dudek [14] introduced a structure of algebras is called BCC-algebras. He also studied some important properties of BCC-algebra in [15-18]. In 2013, Ruma Ajeena al et. [19] presented a coding problem which is included in the public key cryptosystem depended on the bivariate polynomial reconstruction problem (BPRP). The Reed-Solomon code is used in such type of (PKC) based on (BPRP), also see [20]. Recently, in 2021, Z. R. Mousa, A. T. Hameed and R. K. K. Ajeena [21] proposed a new algebra is called ARZ-algebra which is a generalization of the concept BCC-algebra. In this work, an ARZ-valued function are defined and investigated some related properties. The ARZ-block code is created based on an ARZ-valued function. Every finite ARZ-algebra determines ARZ-block code and the converse is true.

The outline of this work is: Section 2 includes two parts related to the basic facts of BCC-Algebra and the proposed ARZ-Algebra. Section 3 presented the proposition of the ARZ-binary block code. Some new definitions and theorems are given and proved as new results. Some examples are discussed to explain these results. Section 4 draws the conclusions.

2. Mathematical Background

This section discusses two parts, first one, it displays the basic facts of BCC-algebra and in the second part, it explains the important concepts related to our proposed of the ARZ-code, which is a ARZ-algebra.

2.1. Basic Facts of BCC-Algebra

This section discusses the fundamental facts of BCC- algebra as follows.

Definition 2.1.1. (BCC- algebra [14]). A BCC-algebra $(X, *, 0)$ is a nonempty set together with two binary operations $*$ and 0 , for all $x, y, z \in X$, the following condition are hold:

- i. $((x * y) * (z * y) * (x * z)) = 0$,
- ii. $0 * x = 0$,
- iii. $x * 0 = x$,
- iv. $x * x = 0$,
- v. $x * y = 0$ and $y * x = 0 \Rightarrow x = y$.

In BCC-algebra $(X, *, 0)$, the relation (\leq) here can be defined by

$$x \leq y \Leftrightarrow x * y = 0.$$

Proposition 2.1.1. (Properties of BCC- algebra [14]). Suppose $(X, *, 0)$ is a BCC- algebra. For all $x, y, z \in X$, the following properties are satisfied:

- 1. $z * z = 0$,
- 2. $z * (x * z) = 0$,
- 3. $x = (x * 0) * 0$,
- 4. $((y * z) * z) * y = 0$,
- 5. $0 * x = 0 * y \Rightarrow x = y$.

Proposition 2.1.2. (Properties of BCC- algebra with an operation (\leq) [14]).

Suppose $(X, *, 0)$ is a BCC- algebra. For all $x, y, z \in X$, the following properties are satisfied:

- 1. $(x * y) * (z * y) \leq (x * z)$,
- 2. $x \leq y \Rightarrow x * z \leq y * z$,
- 3. $x \leq y \Rightarrow z * y \leq z * x$,
- 4. $z * x \leq z * y \Rightarrow x \leq y$.

2.2. The Proposed ARZ-Algebra

In this section, a ARZ- algebra has been proposed based on a BCC-algebra which is considered as a main point to proposed a new ARZ-code. This algebra is defined as follows.

Definition 2.2.1. (ARZ-Algebra [21]). A BCC- algebra $(X, *, 0)$ is called ARZ- algebra of X , if its satisfied (i-iv) axioms of it and adding to them the axiom (vi) by

$$x * y = 0 \text{ and } y * x \neq 0 \Rightarrow y * x = x, x \neq 0. \quad (1)$$

In ARZ-algebra $(X, *, 0)$, the relation (\leq) here can be defined by

$$x \leq y \Leftrightarrow x * y = 0.$$

Example 2.2.1. (ARZ- algebra [21]). Let $X = \{0, a, b, c, d\}$ and let $*$ be a binary operation defined by the following Table (1).

Table 1: The ARZ- algebra with a set $X = \{0, a, b, c, d\}$ [21].

*	0	a	b	c	d
0	0	0	0	0	0
a	a	0	a	0	a
b	b	b	0	b	0
c	c	a	c	0	c
d	d	d	b	d	0

It is easy to show that $(X, *, 0)$ is an ARZ-algebra.

3. The ARZ-Binary Block Code

Before starting to discuss the proposed ARZ- code that is created based on a ARZ-algebra, some new concepts are defined to build this code as follows.

Definition 3.1. (The ARZ-Valued Function). Let A be a nonempty set and let X be the ARZ-algebra. A mapping $f : A \rightarrow X$ is called a ARZ- valued function (or ARZ- function) on A .

Definition 3.2. (A Cut Function of ARZ-Valued Function). A cut function of the ARZ-valued function f is a map $f_r : A \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$, $r \in X$ such that

$$f_r(x) = 1 \Leftrightarrow r * f(x) = 0, \forall x \in A. \quad (2)$$

Obviously, f_r is the characteristic function. A cut subset A_r of A is the following subset of A :

$$A_r = \{x \in A : r * f(x) = 0\}. \quad (3)$$

Definition 3.3. (The ARZ-Code). Let A be a set has n elements. Suppose a set $A = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ and X is the ARZ-algebra. For each ARZ-valued function $f : A \rightarrow X$, a binary block-code of length n can be defined. In other words, for each equivalence class \tilde{x} of $x \in X$, will correspond to the codeword $w_x = x_1 x_2 \dots x_n$ with $x_i = j$, if and only if $f_x(i) = j$, with $i \in A, j \in \{0,1\}$. This code is denoted by V_x which is called the ARZ-code.

Definition 3.4. (Commutative ARZ-algebra). A ARZ-algebra $(X ; * , 0)$ is said to be commutative if it satisfies for all $X, Y \in X$,

$$X * (Y * X) = Y * (X * X), \text{ i.e., } X \wedge Y = Y \wedge X.$$

Definition 3.5. (Implicative ARZ-algebra). A ARZ-algebra $(X ; * , 0)$ is said to be implicative if it satisfies for all $X, Y \in X$ $X = X * (Y * X)$.

Definition 3.6. (Partial Order Relation). Let V be a binary block-code. If $w_x = x_1 x_2 \dots x_n$ and $w_y = y_1 y_2 \dots y_n$ are two codewords in V . On a code V , a partial order relation is defined by

$$w_x \preceq w_y \Leftrightarrow y_i \leq x_i, i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}. \quad (4)$$

Proposition 3.1. Let (X, \leq) be a finite partial ordered set with the minimum element 0. A binary relation $*$ on X is defined by

$$\begin{cases} 0 * x = 0 \text{ and } x * x = 0, \forall x \in X, \\ x * y = 0 \text{ if } x \leq y, \forall x, y \in X, \\ x * y = x \text{ if } y < x, \forall x, y \in X, \\ x * y = 0 \text{ and } y * x \neq 0 \Rightarrow y * x = x, \text{ where } x \neq 0 \text{ cannot be compared.} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Then the algebra $(X, *, 0)$ is

- i. Commutative and implicative ARZ-algebra. Then the ARZ-code is existed.

- ii. Not commutative and implicative ARZ-algebra. Then the ARZ-code is existed.
- iii. Not commutative and not implicative ARZ-algebra. Then the ARZ-code is existed.
- iv. Commutative and not implicative ARZ-algebra. Then the ARZ-code is existed.

Proof. Based on Definitions (3.4) and (3.5), the proof is directly done. ■

Example 3.1. Let $(X, *, 0)$ be a ARZ-algebra as shown in Table (2).

Table 2: The ARZ- algebra with a set $X = \{0,1,2,3\}$.

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	1	1
2	2	2	0	2
3	3	3	3	0

Based on Definitions (3.4) and (3.5), the ARZ-algebra $(X, *, 0)$ is a commutative and an implicative.

Definition 3.7. (The Matrix Associated to the Code V). Let V be a binary block-code with n codewords of length n . The matrix $M_v = (m_{ij})_{i,j \in \{1,2,\dots,n\}} \in M_n(\{0,1\})$ with the rows consisting of the codewords of V is called a matrix associated to the code V .

Definition 3.8. (Lexicographic order) A lexicographic order \leq_{lex} is a totally ordered set (V, \leq_{lex}) of a binary block code V . This means that

$$w_1 \geq_{lex} w_2 \geq_{lex} \dots \geq_{lex} w_n .$$

Theorem 3.1. Suppose the relations in Equation (5) are hold. If the codeword $11\dots 1 \in V$ and let M_v be an upper triangular matrix with $m_{ii} = 1$, for all $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$. Then, there are

- i. A set A with n elements.

ii. An ARZ-algebra X and a ARZ- valued function determines the ARZ-code V and the converse is true.

Proof. Let $V = \{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n\}$. Based on Definition (3.8) of the lexicographic order \leq_{lex} results to (V, \leq_{lex}) is a totally ordered set. This means that

$$w_1 \geq_{lex} w_2 \geq_{lex} \dots \geq_{lex} w_n .$$

This leads to $w_1 = \underbrace{11\dots1}_{n-time}$ and $w_n = \underbrace{00\dots01}_{n-time}$. Now, one can get $w_1 \preceq w_i$, for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ based on Definition (3.6) of a partial order set (V, \preceq) on V . In a set (V, \preceq) , it is easy to see that $w_1 = 0$ is the zero element and w_n is a maximal element. Binary operation $*$ is defined on (V, \preceq) as given in proposition (3.1), this leads to $X = (V; *, w_1)$ is an ARZ-algebra and the ARZ-code V is isomorphic to ARZ-algebra C_n .

If suppose $A = V$ and the identity map $f: A \rightarrow V$ such that $f(w) = w$ as a ARZ- function, then f can be decomposed into family of maps

$$V_{cn} = \{f_r : A \rightarrow \{0,1\} / f_r(x) = 1, \text{ if and only if } r * f(x) = 0, \forall x \in A, r \in X\}.$$

The family V_{cn} considers as a binary block-code V relative to the order relation \preceq .

Conversely, if $w_k \in V, 1 < k < n$ and $w_k = \underbrace{00\dots0}_{k-1-time} x_{i_k} \dots x_{i_n}$, where $x_{i_k} \dots x_{i_n} \in \{0,1\}$, then

$$\begin{cases} \text{if } x_{i_j} = 0, \text{ then } w_k \preceq w_{i_j} \text{ and } w_k * w_{i_j} = 0, \\ \text{if } x_{i_j} = 1, \text{ then } w_{i_j} \preceq w_k \text{ or } w_{i_j} \text{ and } w_k \text{ can't be compared therefore } w_k * w_{i_j} = w_k. \end{cases}$$

■

Example 3.2. With the same ARZ-algebra $(X, *, 0)$ that is a commutative and an implicative on Example (3.1), suppose $f: X \rightarrow X$ be an ARZ-function on X which is given by

$$f = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 \end{pmatrix},$$

and its cut subsets are

$$f_0 = f, f_1 = \{1\}, f_2 = \{2\}, f_3 = \{3\}.$$

Then, a cut function f_r of the ARZ-valued function f is computed based on Definition (3.2) as shown in Table (3).

Table 3: The cut function f_r of the ARZ-valued function f of ARZ- algebra with a set $X = \{0,1,2,3\}$.

f_r	0	1	2	3
f_0	1	1	1	1
f_1	0	1	0	0
f_2	0	0	1	0
f_3	0	0	0	1

Thus,

$$V = \{1111, 0100, 0010, 0001\}$$

is a binary block code that is called ARZ-code which satisfies the lexicographic order that is given in Definition (3.8). Now, if

$$V = \{1111, 0100, 0010, 0001\} = \{w_1, w_2, w_3, w_4\}$$

then the ARZ- code V with $*$ operation that is computed in Table (4) forms the ARZ-algebra.

In other words, one can get, based on Definition (3.6), $w_i \preceq w_1$ for $i = 2, 3, 4$. Also, w_2 cannot be compared with w_3 and w_2 cannot be compared with w_4 , w_3 cannot be compared with w_1 and w_3 cannot be compared with w_4 and w_4 cannot be compared with w_2 and w_4 cannot be compared with w_3 .

Table 4: The ARZ-algebra based on the ARZ- code V with $*$ operation.

$*$	w_1	w_2	w_3	w_4
w_1	w_1	w_1	w_1	w_1
w_2	w_2	w_1	w_2	w_2
w_3	w_3	w_3	w_1	w_3
w_4	w_4	w_4	w_4	w_1

Theorem 3.2. Suppose the relations in Equation (5) are hold. Let

- i. V be a binary block-code with n codewords of length m and $n \neq m$, or
- ii. V be a block-code with n codewords of length n such that the codeword $11\dots 1$ is not in V , or
- iii. V be a block-code with n codewords of length n such that the matrix M_V is not upper triangular.

Then, there are

- i. a natural number $q \geq \max\{m, n\}$, and
- ii. a ARZ-function $f : A \rightarrow C_q$ such that the obtained block-code V_{C_n} contains the block-code V as a subset, where A is a set with m elements.

Proof. Let V be a binary block-code $V = \{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n\}$, with codewords of length m . Based on Definition (3.8), the codewords w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n lexicographic ordered is given by $w_1 \geq_{lex} w_2 \geq_{lex} \dots \geq_{lex} w_n$. Suppose $M \in M_{n,m}(\{0, 1\})$ is an associated matrix, as given in Definition (3.7), with the rows w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n in this order.

It requires to extend the matrix M to a square matrix $M' \in M_q(\{0, 1\})$, $q = m + n$, such that $M' = (m'_{i,j})_{i,j \in \{1,2,\dots,q\}}$ is an upper triangular matrix with $m_{ii} = 1$, $\forall i \in \{1, 2, \dots, q\}$. First, the extension of a matrix M is done using Proposition (3.2) which is proved in the following proposition.

Proposition 3.2. If $M = (m_{i,j})_{i \in \{1,2,\dots,n\}, j \in \{1,2,\dots,m\}} \in M_{n,m}(\{0, 1\})$ is a matrix, its rows has lexicographic ordered in the descending sense. Then, it is possible to find a matrix $M' = (m'_{i,j})_{i,j \in \{1,2,\dots,q\}} \in M_q(\{0, 1\})$, $q = n + m$, such that M' is an upper triangular matrix, with $m'_{ii} = 1$, $\forall i \in \{1, 2, \dots, q\}$ and M is a sub-matrix of a matrix M' .

Proof. Let M be a matrix. It is possible to insert in the left side of M , a n new columns of the form $\underbrace{00\dots 01}_n, \underbrace{00\dots 10}_n, \dots, \underbrace{10\dots 00}_n$, this inserting from the right to the left. This results a new matrix H with n rows and $n + m$ columns. In the bottom of the matrix H also adding the following m rows: $\underbrace{00\dots 010\dots 00}_m, \underbrace{00\dots 001\dots 00}_{n+1}, \dots, \underbrace{000\dots 1}_{n+m-1}$, results a matrix M' . ■

Now, If the first line of the matrix M' is not $11\dots 1$ then the row $11\dots 1$ is inserted as a first row and the column $10\dots 0$ as a first column. On the matrix M' , applying

Theorem (3.1) results a ARZ-algebra X_q with q elements, namely $X_q = \{x_1, \dots, x_q\}$, with $x_1 = 0$ which is the zero of the ARZ-algebra X_q . It is also based on Theorem (3.1), one can get a binary block-code V_{X_q} which is a ARZ-Code. Suppose the initial columns of the matrix M are columns in a new matrix M' that have positions $i_{j_1}, i_{j_2}, \dots, i_{j_m} \in \{1, 2, \dots, q\}$. Let $A = \{x_{j_1}, x_{j_2}, \dots, x_{j_m}\} \subseteq X_q$. The ARZ-function $f: A \rightarrow X_q$, $f(x_{j_i}) = x_{j_i}$, $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m\}$ determines the binary block-code V_{X_q} such that $V \subseteq V_{X_q}$. ■

Example. Let $X = \{0,1,2,3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as shown in Table (5).

Table 5: The ARZ-algebra based on $X = \{0,1,2,3\}$ [21].

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0
2	2	2	0	3
3	3	3	0	0

The ARZ-algebra $(X, *, 0)$ is not commutative and not implicative based on Definitions (3.4) and (3.5). Let $f : X \rightarrow X$ be a ARZ-function on X which is given by

$$f = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 \end{pmatrix}.$$

And its cut subsets are $f_0 = f$, $f_1 = \{1,2,3\}$, $f_2 = \{2\}$, $f_3 = \{2,3\}$. So, Table (6), shows the cut function f_r of the ARZ-valued function f of ARZ- algebra.

Table 6: The cut function f_r of the ARZ-valued function f of ARZ- algebra with a set $X = \{0,1,2,3\}$.

f_r	0	1	2	3
f_0	1	1	1	1
f_1	0	1	1	1
f_2	0	0	1	0
f_3	0	0	1	1

Thus, $V = \{1111, 0111, 0010, 0011\}$ is a ARZ-code which is a binary block code. Now based on the lexicographic order, this code can be rearranged by $V = \{1111, 0111, 0011, 0010\} = \{w_1, w_2, w_3, w_4\}$ be a ARZ-code which is a binary

block code that has the lexicographic order. Based on Definition (3.7), it is possible to form the associated matrix $M_V \in M_{4,4}(\{0,1\})$ which is given by

$$M_V = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Using Proposition (3.2), an upper triangular matrix D is constructed on a matrix M_V by

$$D = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Now, a matrix M' is created by

$$M' = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

So, the binary block-code $W = \{w_1, \dots, w_8\}$ whose codewords are the rows of the matrix M' , determines a ARZ-algebra $(X, *, w_1)$. Let $A = \{w_5, w_6, w_7, w_8\}$ and $f: A \rightarrow X, f(w_i) = w_i, i = 5, 6, 7, 8$ be a ARZ-function which determines the binary block-code

$$U = \{1111, 0111, 0011, 0010, 1000, 0100, 0001\}.$$

The ARZ-code V is a subset of the code U .

4. Conclusions.

In this work, each ARZ-algebra X is proved as a ARZ-code which is a binary block-code V and the versa is true, namely each ARZ-code can be recovered as a ARZ-algebra X . Also, some cases on the ARZ-algebra are determined. These cases are: i) commutative and implicative ARZ-algebra, ii) not commutative and implicative ARZ-algebra, iii) not commutative and vi) not implicative ARZ-algebra and commutative and not implicative ARZ-algebra. If one of cases (i-vi) is satisfied, then the ARZ-code is existed. These results are proved mathematically and some examples of the ARZ-codes are discussed.

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